

Notes on the orb-web spider *Afracantha camerunensis* (Thorell, 1899) in South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman¹, Desiré Pelsers² & Hugh Heron³

¹ DippenaarA@arc.agric.za; ² des@earthandoceans.co.za; ³ hughheronescombe@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Notes on the rare orb-web spider *Afracantha camerunensis* (Thorell, 1899) are provided. The species is known from East, West, Central and South Africa. The general morphology of the species is discussed and live photographs are provided, with notes on their lifestyle.

Key words: Afrotropical, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, SANSa Virtual Museum, savanna, webs

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Afracantha* is a monotypic African genus described by Dahl (1914). The type species, *Afracantha camerunensis*, was described from Cameroon by Thorell (1899) as *Gasteracantha brevispina camerunensis*. The species is recorded from seven African countries (World Spider Catalog 2021). They are known as the Spiny-Backed Orb-Web Spiders.

METHODS

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), requests were made for photographs of species for the SANSa Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2012). Several sets of photographs of *Afracantha camerunensis* were received from the public. During surveys, spiders were sampled and the voucher specimens are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida of the Agricultural Research Council—Plant Health and Protection division.

TAXONOMY

Afracantha camerunensis (Thorell, 1899)

Gasteracantha brevispina camerunensis Thorell, 1899: 65 (Df).

Gasteracantha batesi Pocock, 1900: 858, pl. 56, fig. 10 (Df); Dahl, 1914: 252, fig. 7 (f).

Isoxya camerunensis Benoit, 1962: 25, fig. 18

Afracantha camerunensis Emerit, 1974: 29 (Tf from *Isoxya*).

Description: Total length: female 9 mm. Male unknown. Colour: carapace dark orange to black, with white setae on each side; abdomen light orange with black patches and some anterior median white pigment spots dorsally; legs pale brown, bearing clusters of white setae. Carapace broad, with slight indentation between the cephalic and thoracic region; hump is present behind the eye region; lateral eyes close together, situated on carapace border but widely spaced from median eyes; posterior median eyes slightly wider apart

than anterior median eyes. Sternum with posterior tip extending between coxae of leg IV. Abdomen high in lateral view, hard and covered with scattered brown hairs; viewed dorsally, anterior edge rounded, bearing sigilla; two prominent tubercles with sharp tips present posterolaterally and another pair on posterior edge (Fig. 1). Legs short and arranged around the carapace.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Cameroon, Democratic Republic of Congo, Ghana, Swaziland, Botswana, Zambia, South Africa.

FIGURE 1: *Afracantha camerunensis* female, dorsal view, from Kloof (Photo: D. Pelsers).

FIGURE 2: *Afracantha camerunensis* female, from Kloof, dorsal view (A) and lateral view (B) (Photo: D. Pelsler).

LIFESTYLE

On two occasions the web of *A. camerunensis* was spotted in KwaZulu-Natal. The first was in a camp-site in an open area of mown grassland dotted with *Vachellia* trees in the Umgeni Valley (Heron 2017). The spider was suspended in a vertically oriented colourless orb-web with a diameter of about 20 cm and supported by a long bridge line about half a metre wide below an overhead branch of *Vachellia nilotica*.

The orb-web was situated about 2.0 m from the ground. The second web was photographed at Kloof in KwaZulu-Natal (Fig. 3).

HABITAT

The species is known to occur in the shrub and tree layer in the Savanna and Indian Ocean Coastal Belt biomes (Foord *et al.* 2011).

FIGURE 3: *Afracantha camerunensis* female in a dense orb-web at Kloof (Photo: D. Pelsler).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA (FIG. 4)

Eastern Cape: Cwebe Nature Reserve (-32.28, 28.90). **Kwa-Zulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso Wetland Park (Hell's Gate) (-28.00, 32.48); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24) (Haddad *et al.* 2006); Ophathe Nature Reserve (-28.52, 31.66) (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015); uMkhuze Game Reserve (-25.73, 32.00); Umgeni Valley (-29.47, 30.20). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02) (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003).

FIGURE 4: Map showing the distribution of *Afracantha camerunensis* in South Africa

CONSERVATION

An African endemic species previously recorded from six African countries. In South Africa, it is known from three provinces and conserved in five protected areas. Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

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